

The War Between Bitcoin and Bitcoin Cash

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Keywords:

1. Introduction

The scaling debate in Bitcoin has been ongoing for years, and in fact, it has evolved into a war between Bitcoin and Bitcoin Cash. Which one is the real Bitcoin? Will one takeover? Can they co-exist? What is Bitcoin Cash actually? It's a very spicy topic in cryptocurrency and there is so much noise about this war. With my background in both Chinese and western cryptocurrency community, I will give a non-biased report on this war.

2. Aim

To give a non-biased report on the war between Bitcoin and Bitcoin Cash.

3. Material and methods

Based on my research on the topic.

4. Results

A non-biased report on the dispute between Bitcoin and Bitcoin Cash.

5. Conclusions

Both sides have valid arguments and their future remains to be seen.

6. Keywords

Bitcoin, Bitcoin Cash, scaling, Segwit, lightening network, block size.

Author biography

Yuduo Zhang Yuduo has been investing in cryptocurrency and involved in both Chinese and western

cryptocurrency communities. He got his Bachelor of Computer Science degree from the University of Waterloo. He worked as a software engineer before working on investment fulltime.

February 8, 2018